

Newsletter 10 / 2020

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Spread the word

ESiWACE2 Service 1 call for projects for 2021 is now open!

After a year of successful collaborations in accelerating atmospheric and sea ice-ocean modeling, we look forward to another year of working together with climate modeling scientists in Europe. The ESiWACE2 Services create short collaborative projects that offer guidance, engineering, and advice by the ESiWACE2 consortium partners to support exascale preparations for weather and climate models in Europe. All groups developing weather and climate codes - not only the ESiWACE2 partners - can apply to these services. Service 1 targets model developing groups and assists with porting the codes to new hardware platforms, such as GPUs. The call for proposals in ESiWACE2 Service 1 is now open for applications until November 1st, 2020. Please see <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/hpc-userservices> for more information about the call!

Online training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation

This online training course aims to increase scientists' expertise on data analysis and visualisation applied to climate and weather domains, using high-performance data analytics and visualisation tools available from the open source market. Examples of real applications of these tools (i.e., Ophidia and ParaView) in the climate and weather domain will be given.

The course is being organised by CMCC and DKRZ in the context of the ESiWACE2 project and consists of four 2-hour online sessions held on October 6th - 13th - 22nd and 27th, 2020. **The official registration deadline was October 2nd**, but we are still accepting registrations until available places have been filled. Find more information about the training event and the registration at:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/events/hpda-training-2020>

Online training on Domain Specific Languages - registration open!

ESiWACE2 is running an online Domain Specific Language training course in the week starting 23rd of November 2020. **Registration is open until the 30th of October 2020**. Please note that places are limited. The training will introduce the PSyclone and DAWN systems with a combination of presentations and hands-on exercises. More information can be found on the DSL training event page:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/events/esiwace2-dsl-training/esiwace-2-domain-specific-language-dsl-training>

IS-ENES3 First virtual Autumn school on climate data use for impact assessments

In November and December 2020 the IS-ENES3 consortium will organise an Autumn School 'Climate data use for impact assessments'. Members of the IS-ENES3 consortium will explain the developments in the European climate model infrastructure and update the participants about the availability of data products and assessment tools. The course will also provide insights into do's and don'ts of impact studies, and discuss the information needs of the participants. It will be organised as a virtual course with 2 online sessions during six weeks, combined with self-study

and case studies in small groups. There will be no fee for participation. The number of participants will be limited to 20. Find more information on the School programme and the application procedure [here](#).

Third IS-ENES3 call for Access to Advanced Analysis Platforms for CMIP6 and CORDEX !

The IS-ENES3 consortium is broadening access to world-class supercomputers at the national facilities used by research communities in Germany, France, Italy and the UK. These facilities provide access to significant computational resources located next to extensive data collections, including data from CMIP6 and CORDEX. Thanks to funding from EU H2020, the IS-ENES3 project is

able to provide access free of charge to scientists from anywhere in Europe.

With the new Access to Advanced Analysis Platforms, you will be able to (a) log onto a server which has direct access to the filesystem containing the data, we can import additional data on request, (b) run your own software, (c) have access to a large collection of software libraries commonly used to analyse climate model output.

The new application deadline is October 31st, 2020. It is possible to perform test activities before the application to get familiar with the High Performance Computing environment ! If you miss the deadline, a new round of application will be opened with deadline on the 31.05.2021.

Find all the information on these new analysis platforms (including a demo on how to run server side data-near multimodel comparisons), application procedure, and deadlines [here](#).

Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in

- [ESiWACE2 Domain Specific Language \(DSL\) training](#), online, 23-27 November, 2020
- [Training on High Performance Data Analytics and Visualisation](#), online, 6, 13, 22 & 27 October, 2020
- [ECMWF Annual Seminar 2020](#), online, 14-18 September, 2020
- [Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather](#), online, 23-28 August, 2020

News & updates

Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather

From 24 to 28 August 2020, we realised the Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather 2020. The virtual summer school provided five days of learning and debating HPC systems and climate and weather applications. Topics ranged from Parallel Programming, Performance Analysis, Storage Management to Machine Learning and Containers. Daniel Klocke of the German Meteorological Service (DWD) gave the keynote talk, in which he presented his work on global storm- and ocean eddy-resolving coupled climate simulations and the contributions of projects DYAMOND and DYAMOND2. All sessions were recorded and the recordings, together with the presentations and material for each session, are available on the main summer school [web page](#). The summer school

received 162 applications, and 54 participants who attended more than 70% of the event were granted a certificate of participation. More informations can be found here:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/results-1/showroom/summer-school-on-effective-hpc-for-climate-and-weather>.

ECMWF Annual Seminar 2020

The ECMWF Annual Seminar 2020, this year themed on numerical methods for atmospheric and oceanic modelling, took place from 14th to 18th September. The seminar was held entirely online for the first time, which allowed more than 300 researchers from around the world to attend. The 27 speakers presented on various techniques, both operational and under research, for solving the governing equations of atmospheric, wave, ocean and sea-ice dynamics. Sam Hatfield of ECMWF, who is funded through ESIWACE2 WP1, helped to organise the seminar and also delivered one of the 27 invited presentations. Sam talked about the use of reduced-precision floating-point arithmetic to accelerate Earth-System models, focusing on the operational case studies of the atmospheric model IFS and the ocean model NEMO at ECMWF. A report on the outcomes of the seminar can be found here: <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/about/media-centre/news/2020/annual-seminar-presents-latest-numerical-methods-atmospheric-and>

Panel discussion on AI for climate change at Euronews social media 'lives' event

ESIWACE work package leader Peter Dueben has joined a panel at a live event on Euronews that was chaired by Jeremy Wilks and discussed how artificial intelligence and machine learning can help fight climate change. Other guests were ocean and atmosphere modelling expert Rachel Furner from Cambridge University and entrepreneur Iggy Bassi from Cervest, a company that helps governments keep hospitals, factories and power stations safe in a rapidly changing climate. The recording is available on youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Nni4ydHVI9Y>.

Prof. Björn Stevens is the keynote speaker of the SC20

Initiator of the DYAMOND Initiative and one of the directors of the Max-Planck-Institute for Meteorology, Prof. Björn Stevens has been announced as the keynote speaker of this year's Super Computing Conference SC20. Prof. Stevens will discuss how exascale computing is impacting two opportunities that are changing the face of climate science — one arises from what exascale will enable, the other from what it will not, according to SC conference organisers. The announcement can be found at: <https://sc20.supercomputing.org/program/keynote/>.

Snapshots

Atos Bull

In the framework of HPC Service 1 "Model portability and refactoring" in collaboration with NLeSC and The Cyprus Institute, the GPU memory requirements of EMAC, the ECHAM/MESSy Atmospheric Chemistry model, has been reduced by an order of magnitude allowing for simultaneous offload from multiple MPI processes per node and/or increase of chemical mechanism complexity.

In the same framework, the memory consumption of the scanning phase of OBLIMAP, a fast coupler for coupling ice

sheet models with climate models, has been reduced using MPI shared memory feature when running on the same node.

BSC

In collaboration with ECMWF, OpenIFS 43r3v1 has been released and can be downloaded from the FTP. This version is now able to produce outputs in NetCDF format thanks to the integration with the XIOS server. This version (with some other updates in the coming months) will be used as the atmosphere model in the next EC-Earth4.

ORCA36 runs in 512 MareNostrum4 nodes (~25k cores), using half of them for XIOS, with 3D hourly output (340G per output step) using XIOS. We haven't been able to run the model with 49,152 processes, even having 100T memory for NEMO and another 100T for XIOS. This exercise has been a good test to push the machine and the model to the limits.

CERFACS

The first online session on "Code coupling with OASIS3-MCT" was held on July 6th-10th 2020 with 6 participants from LEGOS (France) and the Met Office (UK). The participants' feedback was very positive, and they should now all be able to implement the OASIS3-MCT API in their own codes to build a larger coupled model. CERFACS has also participated in the "Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather" with a presentation on Code Coupling.

CMCC

The first version of the ESDM PAV runtime and the related Python API and CLI have been released. A technical report documenting this initial version has also been prepared and will be uploaded to Zenodo. CMCC is organising, jointly with DKRZ, an online training course on HPDA and Visualisation that will be held during October 2020. Moreover, the outcomes of the Workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling, held in June, have been reported in a white paper (deliverable D2.6) led by CMCC, and published on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/record/4001485>.

DKRZ

With the support of the ESIWACE2 partners, we have completed and submitted the first 18 month interim report of the project and are currently organising the corresponding review with the European Commission.

Together with CMCC in WP5, we have been preparing the first online training on High Performance Data Analytics (HPDA) and Visualisation to be delivered in October 2020.

We have supported MPI-Met to set up and demonstrate a first 1km/1km coupled ICON simulation on Mistral.

ECMWF

Work on the operational implementation of single-precision in NEMO continues, with the first stable climate simulations at 0.25° resolution achieved in July. The changes are mostly error-neutral except for a few regions which show ~1K differences in SST. Development of a flexible single/double-precision atmosphere-ocean coupling framework is now underway.

Met Office

There are several ongoing developments of PScyclone functionality to improve the performance of LFRic: support for mixed precision, support for field infrastructure (e.g. multi-data fields), implementing PScyclone transformations of

LFRic kernels, and, additionally, flexible stencil sizes and 2D stencils to improve the performance of key advection routines.

NLeSC

We are currently experimenting with the use of single precision in DALES as part of the Service 1 collaboration on DALES. We have been setting up a new call for proposals for new Service 1 projects in 2021. Please see <https://www.esiwace.eu/services/hpc-userservices> for more information about the call!

Seagate

Ongoing work includes optimisation of the Clovis backend for ESDM. Upcoming work will involve the provision of a Mero based system for deployment of ESDM.

UKRI / STFC

We co-organised and presented at the Future Technologies session of the summer school on effective HPC for climate and weather (organised by the University of Reading). We are continuing to improve the GPU performance of NEMO using PSyclone and in collaboration with MeteoSwiss with support from DKRZ are working towards the upcoming DSL training workshop to be held in the week starting the 23rd of November 2020.

UniMan

Having all but completed our optimisation work in Task 2.1 (GPU optimisation in the context of DSL development), we continue to work on Technology Watch in Task 2.4 and have begun preparations for the joint workshop with IS-ENES3 on “New Opportunities for ML/AI in Climate Modelling”, which will be held in Spring 2021 (possibly virtually). We have also started discussions with WP5 on upcoming work on optimisation related to ESDM-PAV in Task 5.4.

University of Reading

We have successfully held and organised the first summer school on effective HPC for climate and weather within the scope of ESIWACE2. Now we are compiling the teaching materials and the result of the survey conducted among the participants, which will feed into deliverable D6.1, which is due in month 36 of the project.

Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications

M. Kloewer, P. D. Dueben, T. N. Palmer: Number formats, error mitigation and scope for 16-bit arithmetics in weather and climate modelling analysed with a shallow water model, accepted in JAMES, 2020.

P. Groenquist, C. Yao, T. Ben-Nun, N. Dryden, P. Dueben, S. Li, T. Hoefler: Deep Learning for Post-Processing Ensemble Weather Forecasts, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2005.08748>, 2020.

S. Rasp, P. D. Dueben, S. Scher, J.A. Weyn, S. Mouatadid, N. Thuerey: WeatherBench: A benchmark dataset for data-driven weather forecasting, accepted in JAMES, 2020.

N. P. Wedi, I. Polichtchouk, P. Dueben, V. G. Anantharaj, P. Bauer, S. Boussetta, P. Browne, W. Deconinck, W. Gaudin, I. Hadade, S. Hatfield, O. Iffrig, P. Lopez, P. Maciel, A. Mueller, S. Saarinen, I. Sandu, T. Quintino, F. Vitart: A baseline for global weather and climate simulations at 1.4 km resolution, accepted in JAMES, 2020.

Gijs van den Oord, Victor Azizi, Alessio Sclocco, Georges-Emmanuel Moulard, David Guibert, Jisk Attema, Erwan Raffin, and Ben van Werkhoven: ESiWACE2 Services: RSE collaborations in Weather and Climate, accepted for publication in Research Software Engineers in HPC (RSE-HPC-2020) Workshop at Supercomputing 2020 (SC20), 2020

News from the neighbours

The 5th Workshop on Coupling Technologies for Earth System Models (CW2020) funded by the EU [H2020 IS-ENES3 project](#) was held virtually on September 21st-24th 2020, with one session of 3.5 hours each day, starting at 15h00 (Paris time).

The workshop brought together leading researchers and practitioners in the field of coupling infrastructure for Earth System Models. This workshop was the fifth in the series, started in [2010 in Toulouse](#) and followed by [Boulder USA \(2013\)](#), [Manchester UK \(2015\)](#), and [Princeton USA \(2017\)](#). Topics discussed during the workshops included:

- Coupling technology latest developments
- Use of Coupling Technologies in ESMs: successes and failures, original or ground-breaking applications
- Performance of Couplers and Coupled Systems
- Data assimilation for coupled NWP and Earth System Models
- Integration of coupling technologies into workflows

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